

Comparative Study of Kinetics of HCl and HClO₄ Acid-catalysed Oxidation of Acetophenone by Selenium Dioxide in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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Selenium dioxide¹⁻³ has been used as an oxidising agent both in the absence and the presence of acid, sulphuric acid or perchloric acid. In the literature hydrochloric acid catalysed oxidations by selenium dioxide are not reported. Our experimental study revealed that the reaction between acetophenone and selenium dioxide is catalysed by hydrochloric acid to a much greater extent than either by sulphuric acid or perchloric acid. This prompted us to undertake comparative study of kinetics of HCl and HClO₄ acid-catalysed oxidation of acetophenone with a view to find out the difference in the reacting oxidising species of selenium dioxide and the mechanism.

Results and Discussion

HCl acid-catalysed oxidation: The order of reaction with respect to selenium dioxide is unity (Table 1). The rate of reaction increases with increase in the concentration of acetophenone and HCl acid (Tables 2 and 3). The plots of log *k* vs log [acetophenone] and log *k* vs log [acid] are linear with slope of unity, indicating that the reaction is of first order with respect to acetophenone and HCl. The added neutral salt (KCl) showed no salt-effect, suggesting that the reaction involves a neutral molecule⁴ in the rate-determining step. The rate of reaction increased with increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture (Table 4). A plot of log *k* vs (D-1)/(2D+1) is linear, suggesting the reaction to be of dipole-dipole type⁵.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SELENIUM DIOXIDE CONCENTRATION

[Acetophenone]=0.5 M, HOAc-Water=73.81% (v/v), Temp.=323 K
[Acid]=0.10 M

10 ³ [SeO ₂] (M)	2.5	5.0	7.5	10.0	12.5
10 ⁶ <i>k</i> (s ⁻¹) (a)	34.40	34.19	34.15	34.14	34.00
(b)	5.77	5.72	5.72	5.70	5.69

(a)≡HCl. (b)≡HClO₄.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACETOPHENONE CONCENTRATION

[SeO₂]=0.01 M, HOAc-Water=73.81% (v/v), Temp.=323 K
[Acid]=0.10 M

[Acetophenone] (M)	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.80
10 ⁶ <i>k</i> (s ⁻¹) (a)	27.48	34.14	41.05	54.94
(b)	4.57	5.70	6.84	9.14

(a)≡HCl. (b)≡HClO₄.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF ACID CONCENTRATION

[Acetophenone]=0.50 M, [SeO₂]=0.01 M, HOAc-Water=73.81% (v/v), Temp.=323 K

[Acid] (M)	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20
10 ⁶ <i>k</i> (s ⁻¹) (a)	17.01	34.14	51.99	64.49
(b)	2.80	5.60	8.53	11.44

(a)≡HCl. (b)≡HClO₄.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF PERCENTAGE OF ACETIC ACID ON REACTION RATE

[Acetophenone]=0.5 M, [SeO₂]=0.01 M, [Acid]=0.10 M, Temp.=323 K

HOAc-Water (% v/v)	70.0	73.81	80.0	85.0
10 ⁶ <i>k</i> (s ⁻¹) (a)	15.2	34.1	63.5	200.5
(b)	4.21	5.70	7.08	12.6

(a)≡HCl. (b)≡HClO₄.

HClO₄ acid-catalysed oxidation: The order of reaction with respect to selenium dioxide is unity (Table 1). The rate of reaction increases with increase in the concentration of acetophenone and HClO₄ acid (Tables 2 and 3). The plots of log *k* vs log [acetophenone] and log *k* vs log [acid] are linear with slope of unity, indicating that the reaction is of first order with respect to both acetophenone and HClO₄ acid. The added neutral salt (NaClO₄) has nominal accelerating effect, suggesting that the reaction involves a neutral molecule⁴ in the rate-determining step. The rate of reaction increases with increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture (Table 4). A plot of log *k* vs 1/D is linear, suggesting the reaction to be of ion-dipole type⁵.

The kinetics of HCl and HClO₄ acid-catalysed oxidation of acetophenone by selenium dioxide has been studied at five different temperatures (313–333 K). The plots of log *k* vs 1/T and log *k*/T vs 1/T are linear. The calculated values of activation parameters for the HCl and HClO₄ acid-catalysed reactions are given in Table 5.

TABLE 5—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

	E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	A s ⁻¹	ΔH [*] kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS [*] J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG [*] kJ mol ⁻¹
(a)	56.10	3.49 × 10 ⁶	56.54	-139.4	100.86
(b)	69.10	7.66 × 10 ⁶	69.25	-113.8	107.28

(a)≡HCl. (b)≡HClO₄.

NOTES

The observed kinetic results of HCl and HClO₄ acid-catalysed oxidation of acetophenone by selenium dioxide in aqueous acetic acid under identical experimental conditions show that the rate constant of HCl catalysed reaction is about six times greater than that of HClO₄ catalysed reaction. The enthalpy of activation values clearly point out that HCl acid-catalysed reaction should occur at a faster rate than HClO₄ acid-catalysed reaction, which is in agreement with our observed experimental results. The effect of dielectric constant of the reaction medium suggests that the reacting species involved in the rate-determining step of these reactions should be of different nature.

It is reported² that in aqueous acetic acid in the presence of a strong mineral acid, the species H₂SeO₃⁺ and AcH₂SeO₃⁺ of selenium dioxide are the active oxidising species.

The effect of HCl acid on the rate of oxidation of acetophenone by selenium dioxide is found to be much more pronounced as compared to HClO₄ acid under identical experimental conditions. This probably suggests that in the presence of HCl much more reactive oxidising species of selenium dioxide is generated in the reaction mixture. The most probable reacting species of selenium dioxide, which

The attack of this oxidising species on acetophenone is expected to enhance the formation of enol-selenite ester to a greater extent, since chloride is a better leaving group than H₃O⁺. This supposition seems to be true as the catalytic effect of HCl becomes even more pronounced when reaction solvent is kept close to glacial acetic acid. Under identical experimental conditions ([Acetophenone] = 0.10M, [SeO₂] = 0.01M, [HCl] = 0.10M, temp. = 323 K), the specific rate constant increases from 1.21 × 10⁻³ to 14.3 × 10⁻³ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ when the percentage of acetic acid is increased from 70 to 95% (v/v). However, in the presence of HClO₄, under identical experimental conditions, the specific rate constant increases from 3.16 × 10⁻⁴ to 6.85 × 10⁻⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹.

On the basis of observed experimental results the most probable mechanism of HClO₄ and HCl acid-catalysed reactions between acetophenone and

selenium dioxide is given in Scheme 1 and Scheme 2 respectively.

Experimental

Acetophenone (B.D.H.), selenium dioxide (Loba), HCl, HClO₄, acetic acid, KCl and NaClO₄ (AnalaR) were used. A stock solution of selenium dioxide was prepared in distilled water and standardised iodimetrically. The course of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted selenium dioxide iodometrically³ under pseudo-first order conditions [SeO₂] ≪ [acetophenone] and [acid]. The results are reproducible within ± 2% error. The end-product phenylglyoxal was identified by preparing its phenylhydrazone⁶.

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